

Speculation on Relativistic Momentum/Energy from Information and Space-Time

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 24, 2024

The nonrelativistic form of momentum, mv , is well-known from Newtonian mechanics. Here we speculate that it may be possible to develop the ideas of energy and momentum (in special relativistic form) for a particle with constant velocity from the idea of information and space-time alone. We do this by considering x and bt (b =constant velocity unit conversion) as two orthogonal row vectors of a matrix, i.e. $(x,0)$ and $(0, bt)$. We then note that a particle with rest mass m_0 appears as a particle moving with $\pm v$ as seen from two frames moving with constant $-v$ or v . The information should be the same for the stationary and moving cases. Rest mass m_0 , however, has no direction, while v does, so we create a velocity sign invariant quantity by multiplying the two matrices together (one with v and the other with $-v$) (multiplied by certain factors) and compare with the matrix with row vectors $(0, 0)$ $(0, m_0)$ multiplied by itself. This leads to the emergence of two new concepts for a moving object, momentum and energy, as well as the special relativistic relationship $E^2 - p^2 c^2 = m_0^2 c^4$ from which one may deduce the form of the Lorentz transformation matrix. Applying these ideas to light ($m_0=0$), which is also a moving entity, one finds that $b=c$.

Classical Momentum

Classical momentum is given by mv , where m_0 is rest mass and $v=x/t$ for a constant velocity with $x=0$ at $t=0$. More generally, $v=dx/dt$. We point out that the Newtonian definition of momentum makes use of basic physical quantities such as x , t and rest mass m_0 , which is linked to how hard it is to lift a mass. It may also be linked to how hard it is to move the object sideways with no friction), although this is not obvious, and is discussed elsewhere in the literature.

We take as a starting point the classical notions of m_0 , x and t .

The Emergence of Momentum, Energy and Special Relativity from Information and $x-t$?

We note that in 3-dimensions, one may create three orthogonal vectors $(x,0,0)$, $(0,y,0)$ and $(0,0,z)$ to deal with position. In the case of time for a constant velocity, one has $\text{distance}=vt$. Thus, t multiplied by a velocity has the dimensions of a distance, which is already known in the literature (Einstein's four space). We consider an arbitrary constant velocity b , for the time being and consider x and bt as two orthogonal dimensions, thus writing the matrix (two orthogonal row vectors):

$$\begin{vmatrix} x & 0 \\ 0 & bt \end{vmatrix} \quad ((1))$$

If x changes in time under a constant velocity, for $x=0$ at $t=0$, one has x and $-x$ describing the two velocities, $((1))$ becomes two matrices.

Next, consider the rest mass m_0 . One may have a particle sitting at $x=0$ with m_0 and a clock ticking. This same particle may be viewed by two frames, one moving at a constant $v=x/t$ and the other $-v=-x/t$. The rest mass is a scalar, it is not linked with two directions like velocity. One may ask: Is it possible to create a scalar using ((1)) (for x and $-x$) and link this to m_0 ? In other words, if one has m_0 at rest, this is completely equivalent to the two scenarios of the object moving to the right and left as seen by two moving frames. The same information exists for m_0 at rest and a combined right left motion picture.

We take ((1)) and multiply by m/bt . Here m is possibly a function of v , so in order to be general we distinguish between m and m_0 , with $m(v=0)=m_0$. "m" is the mass as seen by the moving frame.

We then suggest multiplying the modified ((1)) for x by the modified ((1)) with $-x$ to obtain a matrix invariant in a sign change of x and equate this with the matrix consisting of the two row vectors $(0,0)$ and $(0, m_0)$ multiplied by itself in the following way:

$$\begin{vmatrix} mv/b & 0 \\ 0 & m \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} -mv/b & 0 \\ 0 & m \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m \end{vmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

This leads to: $m = m_0 / \sqrt{1-vv/bb}$ ((3))

As a result, the mass as seen in the moving frame (constant v) is not the same as the rest mass in the stationary frame. Furthermore, one starts with the concept of rest mass in the matrix on the RHS of ((2)), but has two concepts on the LHS, mv/b and m . We call the first momentum/ b and the second energy divided by a constant. Thus, from the idea of rest mass, two new concepts arise which are directly linked to constant motion.

One may consider a transformation which yields this relationship. We first write:

$$(mv)(mv) bb + mmbbbb = momo bbbb \quad ((4))$$

Then:

$$\begin{vmatrix} mvb & \\ mbb & \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb} & v/(b\sqrt{1-vv/bb}) \\ -(v/b)/\sqrt{1-vv/bb} & 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb} \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} 0 & \\ mbb & \end{vmatrix} \quad ((5))$$

The matrix in ((5)) is called a Lorentz transformation in the literature. One may note that the matrices in ((2)) really follow from ((1)) in x,t and so the Lorentz transformation should also apply to the vector (x, bt) . Thus, there is a strong connection between (x, bt) and (mvb, mbb) because the latter follows from the former and the idea of information. In other words, the two vectors transform in the same manner. In the literature, they are said to both be 4-vectors.

A question which remains is: What is b ? It is a constant velocity, but it needs to have a constant value it seems. One may note that a photon may move to the right or left with constant velocity c in a vacuum, but has no rest mass. ((5)) is an expression for two new concepts, momentum and energy, which apply to a moving object. One may speculate that these apply to a photon with m_0 set to 0. Then:

$$-P_{pb} + m_{mb} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad p_b = m_b \quad ((6))$$

The photon follows a wave dispersion relationship: $c = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$. If frequency could be associated with $1/\text{energy}$ and wavelength with $1/p$, then the dispersion relationship would match ((6)) and b would equal c . We take this to be the case as it yields a constant value for b which is otherwise unknown.

Implications for x-t

We use ((5)) to describe a transformation for $(0, m_{oc})$, but it could equally apply to (x, ct) . We begin with a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at time t_0 , where t_0 is some constant. The transformation ((5)) is equivalent to stating that the particle as viewed from a frame moving at constant $-v$, must have a velocity v and so be at x, t such that $x/t=v$. Thus, $(0, ct_0)$ must transform to (x, ct) such that $x/t = v$. This implies that one has the transformation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} f(v) & f(v)v/c \\ -f(v)v/c & f(v) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} |0\rangle \\ |ct_0\rangle \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} |vt\rangle \\ |ct\rangle \end{pmatrix} \quad ((7))$$

We make the matrix unitary. In the above information arguments this follows naturally. One may solve ((7)) to find that $f(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. This is an alternative way to obtain the Lorentz transformation which yields the same results as the information approach.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we start with the physical notions of x, t and rest mass m_0 and consider x, bt , where b is a constant velocity unit conversion factor as two orthogonal row vectors of a matrix, i.e. $(x, 0)$ and $(0, bt)$. This follows from $(x, 0, 0)$, $(0, y, 0)$ and $(0, 0, x)$ being represented by orthogonal vectors. We then consider the physical example of a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ for any time. This particle as seen by a frame at a constant speed of v or $-v$, is seen to move, i.e. have a different x', t' and possibly a different mass (v) , m , such that $\text{mass}(v=0)=m_0$. Physically the moving situations are the same as the rest one, but the rest mass has no associated direction.

We take the matrix of $(x, 0)$ and $(0, bt)$ and multiply by m/bt , where $m(v)$ is the mass as seen by the moving frame. We allow for it to differ from m_0 . We then form two matrices, one with v and the other with $-v$ and multiply them together so there is no sense of direction (i.e. one has a scalar). This is then equated to the matrix with row vectors $(0, 0)$ $(0, m_0)$ multiplied by itself because there is equivalent information.

This yields the relationship: $m_{mb} - p_{pb} = m_{ob}$, where $p = mv/b$. As a result, one has two new concepts for a moving object, m and p , while only m_0 exists for a particle at rest. Furthermore, $m = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$. These two new concepts should apply to a photon, so we suggest that $b=c$. Furthermore, the matrices used follow from original $(x, 0)$ $(0, ct)$ matrices, so the above ideas should also apply to x, ct . We show that one may then obtain a Lorentz transformation matrix which applies to both (x, ct) and (pc, E) .

